

is a mission oriented, multi-funder organisation, that guides and accelerates the innovation process that will transform the food system. The EIT Food partners represent several of Europe's leading agrifood companies, research institutes and universities.

EIT Food supports:

- **Innovation:** guides and accelerates food innovation to transform the food system.
- **Education:** offers a mix of online learning and in-person courses at different locations across Europe; ranging from short-term courses, summer schools, online learning, PhD programmes, degree-awarding Master's programmes to certified professional education.
- **Entrepreneurship:** supports innovative, researchers, entrepreneurs, and impactful AgriFoodTech startups, from business propositions, market validation, business acceleration, tech validation to commercial upscaling. Agrifood tech entrepreneurship powerhouse connects thousands of startups to more than 200 leading corporations, universities, research centres, and investors.
- **Public Engagement:** a set of diverse activities that foster a two-way dialogue between specialists and the public.

Three missions:

- **Healthier Lives Through Food:** the three priority areas which can have the most impact are:
 - Improving product choice and supply for a balanced diet for people and planet,
 - Diversifying protein choices for food products,
 - Optimising the nutrient density of food.

- **Net Zero Food Systems:** the four priority areas which can have the most impact are:
 - Agriculture and primary production,
 - Food loss and food waste,
 - Food and beverage packaging,
 - Protein diversification.

Three key enablers to these priority areas are:

- Data and value chain integration and measure, report, verify (MRV) processes,
- Overcoming barriers to behaviour change in the farming community,
- Changing consumer behaviour.

- **A Fully Transparent, Resilient and Fair Food System:** the four priority areas which can have the most impact are:
 - Resilient and sustainable farming practices,
 - Urban integration of food,
 - Radical transformation of the supply chain and new retail models,
 - Extended producer responsibility and true cost accounting.

Two key enablers to these priority areas:

- Digitalisation of consumer communication and labelling to build trust,
- Food insecurity indicators and framework development.

Three High-Value areas:

- **Protein Diversification:** bringing protein diversification to the mainstream for people & planet,
- **Regenerative Agriculture:** enabling farmers to lead the transition to Net Zero,
- **Labelling, Packaging & Transparency:** empowering people in their food choices.

EIT Food partnership model:

<i>Annual fees</i>	Strategic	Delivery	Community
<i>Large</i>	€75,000	€30,000	€2,500
<i>Mid-Cap</i>	€41,250	€16,500	€1,500
<i>Medium</i>	€22,250	€9,000	€1,000
<i>SME</i>	€11,250	€4,500	€500

Source: <https://www.eitfood.eu/>

Impact Funding Framework:

- Collaborative Missions Programme Funding
- Single Project Funding

Deadline: 31st December 2025,

The next submissions windows in 2024: 14th March, 11th July, 14th November

More information: <https://www.eitfood.eu/open-calls>

More information about EIT Food: <https://www.eitfood.eu/>

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